

Tax Revenue Utilization and Economic Development in Nigeria

¹Ashibogwu Nze Kingsley, PhD
³Toneradu Laju Joy

^{1,2,3}Department of Accounting, College of Management and Social Sciences, Novena University, Ogume, Delta State, Nigeria

¹ashibogwukings@gmail.com; ²jubetemi@gmail.com; ³toneradunjoylaju@gmail.com

Abstract

Although, the amount of revenue generated through non-oil tax in Nigeria in the last few decades is enormous, key indicators of economic growth have not perform very well. Therefore, the study examines the impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria. The data which were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and Federal Inland Revenue Service covered the period, 2011-2020. The model was estimated using autoregressive distributed lag bounds testing approach to co-integration for the long-run analysis while an unrestricted error correction model was relied upon to explore the contemporaneous dynamics. The study finds that the trends of tax revenue are unstable with tertiary education tax being relatively more pronounced. Also, the study finds that economic growth had long-run significant relationship with tax revenue components. However in the short run, economic growth is significantly and positively responsive to changes in company income tax by 0.13%, value added tax by 0.07% and tertiary education tax by 0.25% contrary to its 0.43% negative response to changes in petroleum profit tax. The paper therefore recommended that conducive environment such as improved security, affordable leading rate and basic infrastructures that made investment to thrive should be provided.

Keyword: Tax Revenue, Economic growth, Nigeria, ARDL model

JEL Classification: H20, O40.

Introduction

The role of taxation in a nation quest for development has engenders considerable amount of attentions from scholars and practitioners and there are no shortages of theoretical justification in the literature. The primary purpose of government all over the world is the security of lives and property followed by provision of basic infrastructural facilities like good road networks, good and affordable health sector and good education sector. In order for these basic facilities to be provided funds are required and one of the sources of revenue for government is taxation. However, the amount of revenue which can be generated is predicated on the viability of the economy and this affects the ability of government to provide for the citizens. In sub-Sahara Africa (SSA) countries the low level of income hinders taxable revenue even as high level corruption is also an issue so that a quantum of government income is siphoned by politicians and government appointees. Likewise, many tax officials are unqualified while a good number of tax collectors indulge in fraudulent activities thereby posing enormous challenges to the government revenue generation drive. In several instances, fictitious receipts are issued to tax payers so as to aid diversion of revenue collected into private pockets. Similarly, the failure of government to appreciate the sacrifice made in tax payment by way of judicious

utilization of revenue accruing from taxes has made the tax payers to evade tax payment thereby compounding the already deteriorated government revenue (Asaolu et al., 2018). Thus in Nigeria, deplorable road networks are everywhere a common sight while the health and education sectors are in a state of life support.

Although, it is not the intention of this paper to pass judgment on the ability or inability of government in providing these soft and hard infrastructures, but to stress the importance of taxation for a sustainable economy. This is why Edewusi and Ajayi (2019) submit that the aim of government taxation is not only to generate revenue but rather, as key component of fiscal policy, use it to fine tune the economy to achieve macroeconomic objectives of moderate inflation, stable exchange rate, relatively acceptable balance of payments and sustainable economic growth rate. The literature is replete with litany of evidence to the effect that taxation enhances finances of government, spurs provision of public goods, protects infant industries, controls adverse economic conditions and also reduces inequality of incomes (Anyawu, 1997; Afuberon & Okoye, 2014). As presently being conceived, there are several components of taxation which include petroleum profit tax, company income tax, value added tax, tertiary education tax and so on (Adegbie et al., 2020). However, the value added tax and petroleum profit tax are relatively more pronounced and is the major reason why some state governments in Nigeria are agitating for the administration and control of VAT that has been under exclusive control of the federal government.

Given the importance of taxation in the revenue drive of the government, one will expect a robust performance in the indicators of growth. This is not to be as some macroeconomic variables did not perform very well. For instance, average growth of company income tax stood at 13.8% in the period, 2011-2013 but declined to 1.2% between 2014 and 2016 before oscillating to average of 10.0% during the period, 2017-2020. Similarly, value added tax averaged 8.9% in 2011-2013 and rose to all time high of 16.9% in the period, 2017-2020. However, the growth rate of real gross domestic product (GDP) in the period is less than satisfactory as it averaged 5.0% in 2011-2013, plummeted to 2.5% in 2014-2016 and in the period, 2017-2020, economic growth rate became embarrassing as it recorded for 0.8% growth rate. This is why even though taxation accounts for a reasonable size of revenue to the government, there still exist abject level of poverty in Nigeria with over 70% of the population living on less than a dollar a day. Also, available evidence from the CBN statistics puts the unemployment rate at 18.8% in 2018 and over 20.0% in 2020. Also, there is the prevalence of high inflation rate, under capacity utilization in the manufacturing sector, rising debt profile as well as gross deterioration in macroeconomic fundamentals, all of which combine to strangulate the Nigerian economy (Baghebo, 2012). This is contrary to the minimum acceptable living standards of improved health, access to good water conditions, access to knowledge, nutrition and sanitation prescribed by the Millennium Development Goals.

Prior studies indicate positive impact of tax revenue on economic growth (see Edewusi & Ajayi, 2019; Olushlola et al., 2020; Solanke et al., 2020) whilst author such as Amah (2021) finds negative relationship. These inconsistent results of prior studies in the extant literature with respect to the impact of tax revenue on economic growth spurs further investigation in this regard. Therefore, the objective of the study is to assess the extent at which tax revenue contributes to economic growth in Nigeria. The rest of the paper is organized in the following sequence. A brief review of related literature is undertaken in section two. In section three, the

methodology is highlighted while section four presents and discusses the results. Finally, the paper is concluded in section five where recommendations were also postulated.

Literature Review

Taxation has been conceptualized differently in the literature. Eiya (2012) cited in Edewusi and Ajayi (2019) sees taxation as a compulsory levy imposed by government on the income, capital gains and profits of individuals, firms and organizations as a means to generate revenue. In the view of Anyanwu (1997) also cited in Edewusi and Ajayi (2019), tax refers to compulsory payments made by private citizens and organizations to government coffer for the smooth running of administration. Appah (2004) defines tax as a compulsory payments required of the subjects from their asset to government purse for the purpose of providing social amenities and maintenance of security thereby ensuring the wellbeing of the society.

Meanwhile, economic growth refers to a persistent increase in per capita income occasioned by changes in few sectors of the economy while economic development entails a major structural changes in all or several sectors of the economy thereby increasing productive capability leading to increase in output and income (Todaro & Smith, 2006). There can be economic growth in a nation without economic development if the increase in the country's GDP is coming from one or few sectors say oil and gas or information and telecom sectors as in the case of Nigeria. On the other hand, economic development encompasses economic growth. This implies that the changes in the nation's GDP are attributed to changes taking place simultaneously in several sectors of the economy.

There are a number of theories in the literature that attempt to explain the rationale of taxation for the economy. One of such theories is the benefit received theory which postulates that any payment made in purpose of taxation should be a function of the benefit received from the state. This implies that the services provided by the state in the form of provisions of basic infrastructures should be at tandem with the tax paid by economic entity. In this regards, as the state provides the goods and services the citizens who are the beneficiaries should reciprocate the gesture by bearing the costs of the infrastructural amenities provided by the government. Therefore, the essence of the benefit theory of taxation is encapsulated in the justification of payment of taxes (Amah, 2021). According to Musgrave (1959) cited in Amah (2021), the benefit received theory plays a dual role in that it emphasizes principle of justice anchored on relationship contract between the citizens and the state as well as the principle of equity that compel the citizens to pay the amount equivalent to the benefit received. However, the theory has been challenged as the working practicability has been seen as unrealistic since it fails to provide adequate scientific methods for the assessment in monetary team of the benefit the tax payers received from the state in services provided.

From the empirical corridor, Chigbu and Njoku (2015) examine the extent of the impact of tax revenue on economy performance in Nigeria. The study utilizes the ordinary least square (OLS) methodology on a data covering 1994-2012. The study develops three models with the GDP, a proxy for economic growth, unemployment as well as inflation rate as dependent variables. Accordingly, the study finds that custom and excise duties tax, personal income tax, company income tax, value added tax and petroleum profit tax failed to exert significant impact on the dependent variables in all three models. Ogbonna (2016) explores the relationship

between tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria covering the period, 1990-2012. Using a combination of primary and secondary data with a regression technique, the study finds evidence of relationship existing between company income tax and gross domestic product as well as petroleum profit tax and gross domestic product in Nigeria. Akhor and Ekundayo (2016) evaluate the relationship between income generated from indirect taxation and economic growth in Nigeria for the period, 1993-2013. Using the OLS technique, the study finds that economic growth is significant and negatively responsive to changes in value added tax and custom and excise duty revenues in Nigeria during the period of review.

Meanwhile, Okeke et al. (2018) examine the extent of contribution of tax revenue to economic development in Nigeria. The study employs granger causality, co-integration test and a restricted error correction model on a data covering a period, 1994-2016 to determine the relationship between the dependent variable and the explanatory variables. The findings indicate that revenue generated from taxation had statistical significant impact on primary school enrolment, life expectancy as well as per capita income in Nigeria. Asaolu et al. (2018) scrutinize the impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria, 1994 -2015. The study made tax revenue as explanatory variable and disaggregated into value added tax, petroleum profit tax, company income tax as well as custom and excise duties. The study uses autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model to explore the relationship between economic growth and the various tax components. Accordingly, the study finds among other things that in the short run, value added tax had positive impact on economic growth contrary to the negative effect exhibited by custom and excise duties. Manukaji (2018) assesses the impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria covering a period, 1994-2016. The explanatory variables were petroleum profit tax; value added tax, company income tax and personal income tax. Employing a multiple regression model the study finds that all four independent variables had significant positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria. Abomaye-Nimenibo et al. (2018) examine the response of economic growth to changes in tax revenue in Nigeria for the period spanning 1980-2015. The tax component was disaggregated into petroleum profit tax, company income tax and custom and excise duties. Using the OLS technique and co-integration test, the study finds evidence of a long-run relationship between the variables. Likewise, the study further finds that economic growth is significant and positively responsive to changes in custom and excise duties in Nigeria.

Edewusi and Ajayi (2019) study the relationship that exists between economic growth and tax revenue in Nigeria. Accordingly, the study made economic growth as a function of petroleum profit tax, company income tax and value added tax covering the period, 1995-2015. The study finds that only company income tax had significant and positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The study uses the OLS method to explore the contemporaneous dynamics. Olaoye et al. (2019) assess the response of economic growth to changes in tax revenue generation in Nigeria covering a data period, 2003-2017. The independent variables employed by the study were value added tax, petroleum profit tax and company income tax. Utilizing the ARDL model the study finds that only petroleum profit tax had weak significant positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria. In a recent study, Solanke et al. (2020) investigate the effect of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria covering a period of 1980-2014. Whilst the dependent variable is economic growth, a proxy for GDP, the explanatory variables were made up of petroleum profit tax, company income tax as well as customs and excise duties. The study

utilized co-integration and error correction model for the contemporaneous exploration of the relationship. Accordingly, the study finds evidence of long run relationship between the variables. Likewise, the study further finds that economic growth is significant and positively responsive to changes in petroleum profit tax.

In a related study, Olushlola et al. (2020) assess how tax revenue tends to shape the direction of economic growth in Nigeria. Utilizing the multiple regression technique, it was discovered by the study that tax revenue had significant positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria. Uket et al. (2020) aver that the level of contribution from tax to the Nigeria economy is unclear. Their study therefore seeks to determine the impact of tax elements namely companies profit tax, petroleum profit tax as well as value added tax on the growth of the Nigerian economy. The study uses the OLS method on data covering 1994-2018 and finding indicates that economic development in Nigeria is significantly and positively responsive to changes in companies profit taxes and value added tax. Adegbe et al. (2020) document a study that seek to unveil the extent non-oil tax revenue affect economic growth in Nigeria using a data period, 1994Q1-2017Q4. A multipleregressions technique was employed for the study. The study observes thatthe explanatory variables made up of company income tax, customand excise duties,value added tax and tertiary education tax as well ascapital gain tax had significant positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria in the period under consideration. In a more recent study, Amah (2021) assesses the response of economic growth to changes in taxation disaggregated into petroleum profit tax, value added tax as well as company income tax. The study which covers the period, 1999-2017 utilizes the OLS methodology. Accordingly, the study finds that economic growth is significant and positively responsive to changes in petroleum profit tax and company income tax contrary to its negative response to changes in value added tax.

The Model

The model is specified in line with Olushlola et al. (2020) that permit the estimation of the impact of tax revenue on economic growth in Nigeria as follows:

$$GDP = f(PPT, CIT, VAT, EDT).....(1)$$

In long stochastic form, equation (1) becomes:

$$GDP_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 PPT_t + \alpha_2 CIT_t + \alpha_3 VAT_t + \alpha_4 EDT_t + \varepsilon_t.....(2)$$

Where: GDP = gross domestic product at 2010 constant price, PPT = petroleum profit tax, CIT = company income tax, VAT = value added tax, EDT = tertiary education tax. It is expected that an increase in any of the explanatory variables should lead to a corresponding increase in economic growth and vice versa.

Technique of Analysis

The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model was proposed by Pesaran et al. (2001) to test for the presence of short and long run using bound test to co-integration approach. There are two asymptotic critical values involve in the bound tests suggesting whether the variables are I(0) or I(1) or a combination of both. The two asymptotic critical values are lower and upper bound values. In the view of Pesaran et al. (2001), the lower bound value assumes that the variables are I(0) and no more while the upper bound value concludes that the variables are purely I(1). Essentially, the null hypothesis of no co-integration is stated as $H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4$

= 0 as against the alternative hypothesis $H_1: \beta_1 \neq \beta_2 \neq \beta_3 \neq \beta_4 \neq 0$. A Wald test is conducted to obtain F-statistic which is used to test the null hypothesis. If the F-statistic exceeds the upper bound the test signifies the presence of co-integration. On the other hand, the test will accept null hypothesis if the F-statistic falls below the lower bound critical value. In the case the F-statistic falls between the lower and upper bounds critical values, the evidence that the series are co-integrated is inconclusive. The first step in estimating the model is to determine the lag orders suggested by Schwarz Information Criteria (SBC) and Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) using a vector autoregressive (VAR) model. In what follows is the ARDL estimation of equation (2).

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln GDP_t = & \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^K \alpha 1i \Delta \ln GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^K \alpha 2i \Delta \ln PPT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^K \alpha 3i \Delta \ln CIT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha 4i \Delta \ln VAT_{t-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^k \alpha 5i \Delta \ln EDT_{t-1} + \beta_1 \ln GDP_{t-1} + \beta_2 \ln PPT_{t-1} + \beta_3 \ln CIT_{t-1} + \ln \beta_4 \ln VAT_{t-1} + \\ & \beta_4 \ln EDT_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (3) \end{aligned}$$

A crucial import of the ARDL model is the estimation of the long run and the short run together in a single model. Thus, in equation (3), the segment α is the short run while β denotes long run. Accordingly, if a stable long-run relationship is supported by Wald test from Pesaran et al. (2001) Table of value, the second stage will be the estimation of the short-run by replacing all the segment of β in equation (3) by ECM as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \ln GDP_t = & \sigma_0 + \sum_{i=1}^K \sigma 1i \Delta \ln GDP_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^K \sigma 2i \Delta \ln PPT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^K \sigma 3i \Delta \ln CIT_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^k \sigma 4i \Delta \ln VAT_{t-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^k \sigma 5i \Delta \ln EDT_{t-1} + \lambda ECM_t \dots \dots \dots (4) \end{aligned}$$

The ECM_{t-1} is the error correction term while λ signifies the speed of convergence to the equilibrium process. The coefficient of ECM is expected to be negative if there is co-integration between the variables. Pesaran et al. (2001) avers that the constancy of the long-run multipliers should be ascertained by testing for stability of the parameters in the ECM using the cumulative sum of recursive residuals (CUSUM) and the cumulative sum of square of recursive residuals (CUSUMSQ) whose equation has been detailed in Brown, Durbin and Evans (1975).

Unit Root Test

The Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test is conducted to ensure that the series are only integration of order 0 and 1 as the presence of order 2 variable could result in a breakdown of the model. Also, the test is to avoid estimating spurious regression. The ADF test is estimated as follows:

$$\Delta Y_t = C_i + \omega Y_{t-1} + C_{2t} + \sum_{i=1}^p di \Delta Y_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

Where y_t = relevant time series; Δ = first difference operator; t = a linear trend and ε_t = error term. The null hypothesis of the existence of a unit root is $H_0: \omega=0$. Failure to reject the null hypothesis leads to conducting the test on further differences of the series until stationarity is achieved and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Data and Discussion

Although, tax revenues are one key component that spur economic growth in Nigeria, their performance is not totally palatable. Table 1 and Figs 1 and 2 indicate the structure and trend of economic growth and tax revenues made up of petroleum profit tax (PPT), company income tax (CIT), value added tax (VAT) as well as tertiary education tax (EDT). Table 1 shows that the period, 2011-2013 was the one the growth rate of tax revenue was robust except for petroleum profit tax which recorded negative growth.

Table 1: Structure of Economic growth and Tax Revenues (%), 2011-2020

Year	Economic Growth	Tax Revenue			
		PPT	CIT	VAT	EDT
2011-2013	5.0	-3.3	13.8	8.9	30.7
2014-2016	2.5	-21.8	1.2	1.1	-20.1
2017-2020	0.8	12.8	10.0	16.9	19.1

Sources: CBN Statistical Bulletin (2020) and FIRS (2020)

However, the Nigerian economy was in a recession between 2015 and 2016 and this manifested in revenue generated through tax which became embarrassing most especially in petroleum profit tax and tertiary education tax. Meanwhile, the worst period of economic growth was in 2017-2020 and a number of factors were responsible, name the general insecurity most especially Boko Haram in the North East, Banditry in the North West and North Centre and herdsmen-farmers crises in the North Center of Plateaea and Benue.

Fig 1: Trend of Economic Growth Rate in Nigeria

Fig 2: Trend of Tax Revenue in Nigeria

The results are that a number of macroeconomic variables have not performed very well. For instance, the poverty level has continued to increase while income inequality gap has widened than ever. There are a number of abandon projects all over the county while most road networks have become un-motorable even as power supply is epileptic than ever. It must be noted that the bulk of government revenue comes from sales of crude oil whole price is determined at the global market. There is the need for the Nigerian government to diversify the economy from oil to non-oil such as tax revenue and strengthen the revenue collection strategy.

Table 2: Results of unit root test

Augmented Dickey Fuller Test				Phillips-Peron Test		
Variable	Level	First Dif	Order	Level	First Diff	Order
LGDP	-3.81	-4.79	I(0)	-5.82	-7.23	I(0)
LPPT	-2.33	-3.75	I(1)	-3.21	-4.94	I(1)
LCIT	-2.48	-5.33	I(1)	-3.11	-6.34	I(1)
LVAT	-3.89	-4.62	I(0)	-5.35	-6.80	I(0)
LEDT	-2.25	-3.67	I(1)	-3.29	-5.24	I(1)
C.V = 5%	-3.55	-3.56		-3.55	-3.56	

Source: Author’s computation using Eview 9.0

Table 2 contains the results of stationarity test and it can be observed that the series are stationary at both integration of order 0 and 1 at 5% level of significant.

Table 3: ARDL model of estimation

Dependent variable: DLGDP

Variable	Coefficient	Std error	t-statistic	Probability
Constant	0.23	0.14	2.09	0.06
Δ LGDP(-1)	0.08	0.05	1.60	0.08
Δ LPPT(-1)	0.33	0.12	2.76	0.03
Δ LCIT(-1)	0.29	0.11	2.64	0.04
Δ LVAT(-1)	-0.27	0.10	-2.70	0.03
Δ LEDT(-1)	0.31	0.28	1.11	0.69
LGDP(-1)	0.08	0.02	4.00	0.00
LPPT(-1)	-0.65	0.23	-2.82	0.02
LCIT(-1)	-2.31	1.12	2.06	0.05
LVAT(-1)	0.32	0.26	1.23	0.54

LEDT(-1)	0.24	0.07	3.43	0.00
Diagnostic Test				
R ²	0.81			
DW	2.23			
F-stat	3.53			
Serial correlation LM F-Test	0.23 (0.42)			
ARCH LM F-Test	0.52(0.63)			

Source: Author's computation using Eview 9.0

Specifically, GDP and VAT achieved stationarity at level differencing while PPT, CIT and EDT were stationary at first differencing. The unit root test indicates that the first condition for ARDL modeling has been meant. The purpose of the model estimation at this stage is to derive the F-statistic using the Wald test. In Table 3 therefore, the ARDL model is estimated with a lag length of 1 as suggested by AIC and SBC following the VAR estimation. A number of diagnostic tests such as ARCH LM test, serial correlation LM test and model stability test was conducted on the model to determine its robustness. The tests show that the model passes all the diagnostic tests and is satisfactory. Accordingly, Table 4 reveals that the bound co-integration test indicates the presence of co-integration as the computed F-statistic of 8.15 exceeds the upper critical bound value of 4.01. This implies that a long-run relationship exists between economic growth and its determinants.

Table 4: ARDL Bound test for cointegration

K	5 % Level		10 % Level	
	I(0)	I(1)	I(0)	I(1)
4	2.86	4.01	2.45	3.52
Computed F-Statistics = 8.15				

Source: Narayan (2005) Table CI (iii) Case III: Unrestricted intercept and no trend

Table 5 is the final stage of the model which contains the error correction model. Here, the diagnostic tests and the CUSUM plot in Fig 3 that checked the model stability were carried out. The F-statistic is presented with its corresponding p-values in parenthesis.

Table 5: Estimated ECM
Dependent variable: DLGDP

Variable	Coefficient	Std error	t-statistic	Probability
Constant	0.14	0.05	2.80	0.01
Δ LGDP(-1)	0.22	0.08	2.75	0.02
Δ LPPT(-1)	-0.43	0.14	3.07	0.00
Δ LCIT(-1)	0.13	0.04	3.25	0.00
Δ LVAT(-1)	0.07	0.02	3.35	0.00
Δ LEDT(-1)	0.25	0.08	3.12	0.00
ECM(-1)	-0.21	0.05	-4.20	0.00
Diagnostic Test				
R ²	0.64			
DW	2.06			
F-stat	4.12			

Serial correlation LM F-test	0.23(0.51)
ARCH LM F-test	0.32(0.32)

Source: Author’s computation using Eview 9.0

The model passes the diagnostic tests as it is serially uncorrelated, has homoscedasticity and is stable. For instance, the DW statistic indicates absence of serial correlation while the F-statistic shows that the model is statistically significant. Likewise, the fit of the model (R^2), is relatively robust as the explanatory variables account for 64% variation in real GDP, a proxy for economic growth. Observably, the results in Table 5 indicate that all four tax components are statistically significant in the short run in affecting economic growth in the period under consideration. Specifically, company income tax; value added tax and tertiary education tax exhibited positive relationship with economic growth with exception of petroleum profit tax who exerted a negative effect. What this implies is that a change in any of the independent variables has a corresponding impact on economic growth.

For instance, a unit increase in petroleum profit tax decreases economic growth by 0.43% why a 1% increase in company income tax, VAT as well as tertiary education tax led to 0.13%, 0.07% and 0.25% increase respectively in economic growth during the period under review. The result of petroleum profit tax gives credence to the findings of Akhor and Ekundayo (2016), Manukaji (2018) but contrary to Ogundipe and Oluwadare (2019), Solanke et al (2020) and Amah (2021). For the other three variables in the model, Asaolu et al (2018), Manukaji (2018), Edewusi and Ajayi (2019), Uket et al et al (2020) and Adegbie et al (2020) had earlier reached similar findings.

Fig 3: CUSUM Test

However, in the long run the impact of all the explanatory variables on economic growth is significant as depicted by the ECM which is the residual obtained from the long run dynamic model. The negative sign of the ECM coefficient refers to the speed of convergence which is what is expected if there is co-integration between the dependent and explanatory variables. The magnitude of this coefficient implies that it takes approximately a speed of 21% forequilibrium between economic growth and tax revenue components to be restored within a year. Observably, the ECM is dynamically stable as the plots of CUSUM) lie within the 5% critical bounds thereby confirming the stability of the model.

Concluding Remarks

That non-oil taxation strategy is a vital component of economic growth in a nation’s quest for development especially for a developing country like Nigeria is not in doubt. However,

despite the enormous revenue realized from taxation, key economic growth indicators such as unemployment, poverty and infrastructural amenities have not perform very well. Therefore, the study was carried out to assess the relationship between economic growth and tax revenue generation in Nigeria. The study employs descriptive and econometric analysis on data covering the period, 2011-2020. It was observed that the trends of tax revenue are unstable with tertiary education tax being relatively more pronounced. In the long run, all the variables are statistically significant. In the short run, company income tax, value added tax and tertiary education tax had significant positive impact on economic growth against the negative impact of petroleum profit tax. The major conclusion which can be drawn from the study is that non-oil taxation has the potential to grow the Nigerian economy if and only if it is efficiently managed. It is therefore recommended that conducive environment that made investment to thrive should be provided by the government. These include improved security (as the present deteriorating insecurity scares away investors), affordable leading rate as well as provision of infrastructures such as good road networks and stable power supply. This will reverse the current negative impact of petroleum profit tax on economic growth. Finally, government may consider moderate reduction in VAT so as to increase the demand for goods and services leading to increase in productivity.

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